

The Factors Enabling Adoption of E-learning Post Covid-19 Pandemic for Teaching and Learning in Selected Secondary Schools in Tanzania

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Abstract:

This study assessed the factors enabling adoption of e-learning post Covid-19 pandemic in selected secondary schools in the Dodoma region of Tanzania. Specifically, the study wanted to determine the use of e-learning post, Covid-19 pandemic from the perspective of students, teachers, and ICT support staff in selected Secondary schools in Dodoma, Tanzania; to identify strategies used by teachers to teach e-learning all through the post-covid-19 pandemic in selected Secondary schools in Dodoma, Tanzania; and to identify factors enabling students to use e-learning during the post-covid-19 pandemic in selected Secondary schools in Dodoma, Tanzania. The

study was guided by the Technology acceptance (TAM) as advocated by Davis in 1989 in creating variables and constructs used in the study. The study employed a mixed research approach in which both quantitative and qualitative techniques were used. The study used a sample size of 492 obtained by simple random sampling. The findings showed that e-learning is associated with various perceptions of teachers and students which were identified as follows; 47.8% are of the view that e-learning lacks a proper implementation mechanism in secondary schools. The factors for the adoption of e-learning were such as perceived ease of use, attitude towards use and perceived usefulness which revealed that e-learning is good system used in teaching students in secondary schools. This study recommends on the selection of the right e-learning software solution compatible with contemporary secondary school. This study also recommends for the creation of the multi – format contents to the user, such as reading e-books, viewing videos, and listening to audiobooks, learners may learn concepts and gain information via e-learning solutions. The study also recommends to stakeholders to ensure overcoming of the implementation challenges of e-learning.

Keywords: *e-learning, Students, Teachers, Adoption, Secondary Schools.*

Introduction

E-learning has greater significance in secondary education. It offers the flexibility of accessing education anywhere and anytime (Kisanjara et al., 2017). Currently, facilities like the internet, which enhances access to e-learning, facilitate the effectiveness and widespread of e-learning

everywhere (Kisanga & Ireson, 2015). The sudden eruption of COVID-19 in 2019 globally has brought to light the complexity of immediately moving from local learning to remote learning platforms (Mukuka et al., 2021). In Tanzania the only solution government had, was to close schools to stop the COVID-19

virus from spreading. This strategy totally disturbed the entire education system (Kamal & Illiyan, 2021). During the pandemic students failed to complete their syllabi on time because they had no learning option to turn to, as a result of school closure. Tanzania's major "Technology Rush" in education systems was triggered by the COVID -19 with the stakeholders exploring what solution technology could offer during school closure (Mtebe et al., 2021). Thus, in some instances, the use of ed-tech was the one of the options for students to continue learning while at home. Though ed-tech, teachers and students could integrate into the classroom via online platforms (Mwakyusa & Ng`webeya, 2022). Moreover, the ministry of education emphasized the implementation of the ICT policy integrated in basic and secondary school. It moreover emphasized the use of TV, internet led sites (Youtube) and radio broadcasts in teaching different subjects during the pandemic (Manyengo & Manyengo, 2021). Despite the inadequacy of physical resources in schools, the outbreak of COVID-19 triggered the country towards the adoption of e-learning. The adoption of e-learning enables students from both urban and rural areas to access educational materials which leads to high-quality learning (Mwakyusa et al., 2016). While the teaching and learning system changed during the COVID-19 outbreak, some schools preferred the continued use of the system even after the pandemic. While some schools considered the system easy to use during the teaching and learning, others considered the technology itself as simple to use. Moreover, capability and readiness of using the technology triggered the continuous use of the technology. Although these factors have been considered important in the continued use of e-learning, they are not sufficient in explaining the continued adoption of e-learning after the pandemic. Thus, the research assessed the factors enabling adoption of e-learning after the COVID-19 disease in selected Secondary schools in Dodoma, Tanzania. The specific objective of this study was

- To determine the use of e-learning post the Covid-19 pandemic for teaching and learning

from the perspective of students, teachers, and ICT support staff in selected Secondary schools in Dodoma, Tanzania.

- To identify strategies that are used by teachers in adopting e-learning all through the post-covid-19 pandemic for teaching and learning in selected Secondary schools in Dodoma, Tanzania.
- To identify factors enabling students to use e-learning during a post-covid-19 pandemic in selected Secondary schools in Dodoma, Tanzania.

Material and Methods

This study adopted a mixed research approach, under this approach the researcher was able collect quantitative data by using Likert Scale Questionnaires and qualitative data by using interview and reviews of various documents. This study used descriptive research design, through descriptive research design the researcher was able to identify characteristics, frequencies, categories of the research problem. In this study data was analysed using SPSS for quantitative data and qualitative data was analysed using thematic procedure. Quantitative data was analysed Mean, Standard deviation, correlation and lastly the researcher employed regression too and qualitative techniques and the findings obtained were as follows.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics

Characteristics	Category	Frequency	Per cent
Age	15 - 17 Years	305	63.1
	18 - 24 Years	178	36.9
Gender	Male	137	28.4
	Female	346	71.6
Level of Education	Form Three	275	56.9
	Form Four	208	43.1
Experience on e-learning	First time user	250	51.8
	Ordinary user	165	34.2

Qualified user	32	6.6
I don't know	36	7.5

The findings of this study show that 305 (63.1) of the students had the age of between 15 – 17 years. On the other hand, 178 (36.9%) were between 18 and 24 years. The findings also reveal that 137 (28.4%) of the respondents were

male while 346 (71.6%) of them were female. On the level of education, it was revealed that 275 (56.9%) of the respondents were from three students, while 208 (43.1%) were from four students. Lastly in relation to experience on e-learning the study revealed that 250 (51.8%) of the respondents were first time users, 165 (34.2%) ordinary users, 32 (6.6%) were qualified users and 36 (7.5%) being those with no any knowledge about the use of e-learning.

Table 2. Teachers and Students Perspectives on E-Learning

Teachers and Students Perspectives on e-learning	1 F (%)	2 F (%)	3 F (%)	4 F (%)	5 F (%)
e-learning lacks a proper implementation mechanism in secondary schools	48(9.9)	22(4.6)	4(0.8)	178(36.9)	231(47.8)
Schools and government don't have a proper investment in this system	40(8.3)	32(6.6)	0	208(43.1)	203(42.0)
Students were not ready to accept the use of this study	26(5.4)	36(7.5)	16(3.3)	196(40.6)	209(43.3)
Teachers lacks proper knowledge on the application of e-learning	36(7.5)	8(1.7)		158(32.7)	281(58.2)
e-learning should be a regular system of learning not until when there are challenges		93(19.3)	49(10.1)	189(39.1)	152(31.5)
Risk assessment associated with e-learning should be determined and solved	18(3.7)	56(11.6)	27(5.6)	221(45.8)	161(33.3)
The use of e-learning should include in the curriculums and syllabus	35(7.2)	54(11.2)	16(3.3)	186(38.5)	192(39.8)

From findings depicted in Table 2 of this study, it can be established that 47.8 % of the respondents pinpointed that e-learning lacks a proper implementation mechanism in secondary schools, this is due to the fact that e-learning adoption was forced to be applied while most of the schools in Tanzania were not prepared to accept and use. Also, it was noted that 43.1 % of the respondents pinpointed that schools and government do not have a proper investment in this system. This was because the government did not prepare budgets, expertise and other infrastructural requirement for the implementation of e-learning process in secondary school. On the other hand, 43.3 % of the respondents, among them students, were not ready to accept the use e-learning because the system was not yet familiarized to the students hence it was totally a new thing to them and its quick adoption was associated with a number of limitations. The findings of this study also

revealed that 58.2% of the respondents who participated in this study agreed that teachers lack proper knowledge on the application of e-learning. Moreover, 45.8% of the respondents suggested that e-learning should be a regular system of learning not until when there are challenges. With regard to risk assessment, 46.2% of the respondents established that the risk assessment associated with e-learning should be determined and solved, and 39.8 % of the respondents were of the view that the use of e-learning should be included in the curricula and syllabi.

Strategies Used to Enhance E-Learning

Provision of prior clarifications and attention to students and their parents

Since the learning process was carried out at home using an internet network or online class and to ensure that the learning process can run smoothly, effectively and students remain

interested in learning, e-learning educators explained to students and their parents about the importance of learning in any situation. Such clarifications were done before the learning process took place. Students and parents were given the understanding that learning is necessary and that through learning they can be smart, by learning they can get a lot of knowledge, will be rewarded and exalted by God. The school heads ensured that such all teachers gave such clarifications to their students and teachers.

Preparation of brief, clear, easy to understand and interesting learning materials

During the COVID-19 pandemic the strategies implemented by teachers to increase students' interest in learning included preparing learning materials that are brief, clear and easy to understand, interesting, adapted to the media and learning systems used. Learning with online system was a matter that was unclear and had not yet been understood. In online learning students were not free to ask questions about materials that were not understood. Presenting learning material in a brief, clear, interesting and easy to understand manner was necessary so that student's learning remained high and students did not get bored and remain enthusiastic in learning.

Choosing a simple and attractive learning media

Another strategy used by teachers in facilitating e-learning was choosing a simple and attractive learning media. Media were simple in terms of affordable costs, easy to use by teachers and students in the learning process. Interesting means not boring and can foster students learning. The media used were such as WhatsApp, and Zoom classrooms. However, using zoom was considered less secured and required a lot of internet quota, so zoom was only used in few sessions.

Conducting regular and continuous evaluations

Evaluation is an activity carried out to determine the level of progress or development of students after carrying out learning process at a certain time. Evaluation activities are carried out periodically and continuously. Evaluation activities are carried out not only to measure the level of progress and development of students after following the learning process but also to evaluate the effectiveness of methods, media, learning strategies, applied to increase students interests and motivations. By regular and continuous evaluation students will always prepare themselves by reading books and learning materials that they have learned.

Provision of individualized and personalized teaching materials

The COVID 19 pandemic led to a realization that digital material can in some cases replace physical materials. This means that more information is needed on how this has helped to increase individualized teaching materials. Often all class materials are offered at the start of the course enabling students to learn at their own pace. This created a self – motivated learning environment where accountability is placed on the students.

Training teachers on digital and technological skills

Teachers were given some training and development programs to enhance their teaching process. The educational background of the teachers was considered because several schools had unqualified teachers to teach in levels such as early child development. The majority of teachers revealed that online teaching was such a platform that made every teacher familiar with different kinds of resources and it always provided an opportunity for developing innovation and creativity. Similarly, virtual mode provides ample chances to boost communication towards various online sessions. E-learning created opportunities to access and share information more easily and readily for the teachers in private schools. The use of asynchronous strategy reduced signal interference, internet data limitation and time limitation. The use of WhatsApp groups reduced obstacles when the e-learning systems could not

be accessed. These findings are positively supported by Camilleri and Camilleri (2022) who revealed the importance of providing appropriate facilitating conditions to improve perceptions and attitudes towards interactive conferencing software. The results show that

students are willing to participate and engage in virtual meetings through video conferencing programs. From this study, it can be established that the most convenient strategy used to enhance e-learning is video conferencing.

Table 3. Linearity and Multicollinearity

		EL	PU	PEU	ATU
EL	Pearson (r)	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N	279			
PU	Pearson (r)	.116	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.005			
	N	279	279		
PEU	Pearson (r)	-.184**	.023	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.696	.002		
	N	279	279	279	
ATU	Pearson (r)	-.039	-.071	.315**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.519	.235	.000	
	N	279	279	279	279

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3, shows that the overall correlation between the independent and the dependent variable is 0.01 which depicts a positive and significant correlation between the independent and the dependent variables. more specifically PU (r (279) > 279, p < .005, PEU (r (279) > .023,

p < .002 and ATU (r (279) > 315, p < .000). From the specific findings the study revealed that the predictors of e-learning namely PU, PEU and ATU are positively correlated to e-learning. Moreover, results showed that there is a linearity and also there were no multicollinearity issues.

Table 4. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin Watson
1	.622 ^a	.549	.539	.674	1.267

Findings as presented in Table 4 reveal the summary of the model in which findings reveal that the model fits the data. Findings shows that the three independent variables (ATU, PU, PEU and EL) have a combined factor loading of .622 (approximately 62%) that is the explanation of the regression equation. the R square value was loaded at .549 (55%) and adjusted R-square of 5.39 (54%). These results mean that there are three independent variables explaining about 62% of the dependent variable (adoption of e-learning, adjusted to 55% which means the remaining percentage could be explained by additional other factors which are outside the

suggested ones. According to Saunders et, al (2016) and Malhotra (2009), R-square value range of 50% - 70% imply a moderate effect of the independent variable to the dependent variable. While the model summary was determined, the researcher wanted to test for autocorrelation. The researcher used the Durbin Watson test and the value of 1.662 was obtained. The Autocorrelation is a violation of one of the parametric assumptions. When autocorrelation values are close to 4 it suggests a negative autocorrelation and when they are between 1.5 and 2.5, they imply absence of autocorrelation.

In this study the value of 1.267 suggested that autocorrelation does not exist.

Table 5. ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8.548	3	2.849	14.56	.003 ^b
	Residual	164.771	275	.599		
	Total	173.319	278			

Findings presented in Table 5 clearly depict that ANOVA testified the interaction effects between variables and within groups; to confirm and to relate mean value effects of value

variables. The F-test was 14.56 and was statistically significant as the p-value was .003 below the estimated 0.05.

Table 6. Regression Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.159	.335		12.416	.000
	PU	.307	.051	.123	2.090	.003
	PEU	.431	.041	-.197	-3.175	.002
	ATU	.230	.058	.032	.517	.005

Findings as presented in Table 6 depict that Perceived Usefulness has the coefficient of .123 ($\beta = .123, p < .003$). This shows that perceived usefulness is positive and significantly related to e-learning. Thus, a unit increase in perceived usefulness increase e-learning adoption by 3.07. The empirical literatures support that e-learning is influenced by usefulness when the teachers are engaged with students and the subject matter in an e-class, they are likely to improve the performance thereby explaining the direct impact of technology on learning. However, the opposite is true. Also, it was revealed that the perceived ease of use has a score of .197 ($\beta = .197, p < .002$), which means that there is a positive and significant relationship between perceived ease of use and e-learning and this results further provides that a unit increase of perceived ease of use increases adoption of e-learning by 4.31. Lastly attitude towards use scored 0.32 ($\beta = .032, p < .005$). Such findings imply that there is a positive and significant relationship between attitudes towards use and e-learning adoption. The study also pinpoints that the increase of attitude towards use by 1

unit, increases the adoption of e-learning by 3.2. Thus, it can be established that students showed positive perception about e-learning. Moreover, students felt that e-learning has significant impact on their learning.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study recommends on the selection of the right e-learning software solution compatible with contemporary secondary schools. This is because without selecting the ideal e-learning system, including an LMS, virtual classroom software, online examination software, and digital libraries, no educational institution or company can successfully deploy eLearning. By using cloud-based e-learning solutions, you may quickly do away with the requirement to create and manage an on-site IT infrastructure. However, it should be kept in mind that e-learning solutions vary from one another in a variety of ways, including functionality, usability, accessibility, and security.

This study also recommends for the creation of the multi – format contents to the user, such as reading e-books, viewing videos, and listening to audiobooks, learners may learn concepts and gain information via e-learning solutions. Only by giving students access to a wide range of digital resources, including papers, presentations, e-books, info graphics, videos, audiobooks, and podcasts, will enable the school to make e-learning successful and sustainable.

The study also recommended that responsible stakeholders should ensure overcoming of the implementation challenges of e-learning. Since there are different implementation problems for e-learning. For instance, increasing access to mobile devices and the internet, boosting internet speed, and modernizing teacher training programs are strategies to improve the e-learning. By keeping students interested, engaged, and motivated, educational institutions look into strategies to increase information retention.

Recommendation for Further Study

This study recommends further research to be conducted on the challenges facing implementation of e-learning post Covid – 19, this study will create a comparative assessment of the different implementation challenges toward e-learning and hence improves the application of e-learning in secondary school even after Covid 19.

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